

ISic0028

I.Sicily inscription 0028

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1

: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2

: mm

Text

1. Ti(berio) · Claudio · Herodi
2. ano · c(larissimo) · v(iro) · leg(ato) · prov(inciae) · Si cil(iae) · iudici · rarissi
4. mo · patrono · col(oniae)
5. Panhormit(anorum) · princi
6. pales · viri · ex · aere col
7. lato d(ono) · d(ederunt)

Apparatus

Text of

Translation (en)

To Tiberius Claudius Herodianus, a man of most illustrious fame (i.e. of senatorial class), most extraordinary judge, patron of the colony of Panhormitans. The foremost men (of the colony) gave (this monument) as a gift from communally collected coin.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491788

EDR 137870

EDCS 22000872

Bibliography

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Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 43

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